

Adaptive Null-Steered Interference-Rejection For a Mobile Satellite Receiver

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Abstract—One of the most useful applications of antenna arrays is interference rejection. This paper describes an antenna array that was designed for the sole purpose of rejecting interference of a satellite receiver from a close-proximity jamming source. Since this jammer can move relative the satellite antenna, the antenna array must adaptively adjust its null direction accordingly. The system consists of a six-element array of circular fractal patch antennas in conjunction with a receiver channel that is dedicated to interference detection and tracking.

1. INTRODUCTION

Electromagnetic interference can disrupt mobile communications in both military and commercial mobile applications. This is especially true when a high-power terrestrial source is in close proximity to a mobile satellite receiver. This can be especially problematic when the mobile receiver passes fixed high-power radio sources, or perhaps even more problematic, when a military vehicle is in the presence of a radar or jamming source that is either onboard or on a nearby vehicle within the same convoy. In this case, the local interfering signal would likely overpower the weak satellite signal, even if that interfering signal were out of the frequency band of the desired signal's channel, due to non-ideal filtering. To exacerbate this problem, many of these jamming sources are ultra wideband (UWB) and consist of electromagnetic energy spread over a very large bandwidth that may

overlap the frequency channel of the desired satellite signal. In this case even the fraction of the UWB interfering power that is in-band, could potentially overpower the desired satellite signal. One way to mitigate this interference is with adaptive beam steering from a phase-array antenna.

2. METHODOLOGY

Two general methods of adaptive beam steering were considered for interference rejection, both of which would result in a favorable signal to interference ratio (SIR). The first method is to simply steer a narrow main beam toward the desired source, as illustrated in Figure 1. Presuming that the interfering signal is outside this high-gain main beam, the satellite receiver would most likely detect the desired satellite signal with greater received power than the interfering signal, resulting in a useable SIR. It is reasonable to assume that the satellite and terrestrial interference signals would arrive from different angles, except for the less likely case when the satellite direction is near the horizon, and both sources just happen to share the same azimuth, or compass direction. There are other exceptions to this assumption as well, such as the mobile receiver in a canyon, while the interfering source is on a hill, or the mobile is in an urban environment with the interfering source on a tall building, etc. However, these scenarios would create satellite communication disruptions even without the presence of interference, so these less likely scenarios will not be considered here.

Figure 1 - Antenna beam steered toward the satellite signal, S and rejecting the interfering signal, I .

While this main-beam steering method is theoretically possible, it is impractical due to the required array size. For a reasonably narrow beamwidth, the array would require a two-dimensional array with several elements in each direction. The beamwidth represented in Figure 1, required eight elements in the dimension represented, with half-wavelength spacing between each element. This would result in seven half-wavelengths in each dimension, not including the physical size of the antenna elements. Realistically, this particular array would be at least four wavelengths, 4λ long. The usual approximation for the half-power beamwidth (in radians) from a uniformly excited array is [1]

$$HP = 0.886 \frac{\lambda}{Nd} \quad (1)$$

From equation 1, a 20-degree half-power beamwidth would require five wavelengths in each horizontal dimension. If we consider UHF frequencies below 1GHz, a rectangular two-dimensional array would measure approximately one meter by one meter, not counting extra for the physical elements. For our application, a frequency near 440MHz was of interest, requiring an array measuring well over two meters across. Therefore, we rejected this approach in favor of a second approach.

A second beam-steering method, and the approach that we chose to implement, is to steer a null in the direction

of the interfering signal in order to reject it. The advantage of this null-steering approach over the main-beam steering approach is that we do not require high gain, or a narrow main beam to produce a null. Without the need for high gain, the aperture size can be made much smaller. In fact, the simplest null-steering array only requires two elements that are spaced one-fourth wavelength, $\lambda/4$ apart, as shown in Figure 2 along with its resulting radiation pattern.

While relatively small and simple to build, this array would only allow us to toggle the null from left to right, i.e., two opposite compass directions, by switching the 90-degree phase shift from one feed to the other. Since we need to steer the null horizontally in all 360 degrees of azimuth, we chose to use a 6-element circular array with $\lambda/4$ radius, as shown in Figure 3.[2] This configuration allows us to steer azimuthally, (ϕ) as well as in elevation, (θ). However, since in our application the interfering signal will always be along the horizon, and the desired satellite signal will be elevated above the horizon, we will aim our main beam toward horizon ($\theta = 90^\circ$), which in turn creates a null 180 degrees behind the main beam, also to the horizon. Since the array size is intentionally insufficient for high gain, there will be sufficient coverage at high elevation angles, even to the zenith ($\theta = 90^\circ$). Therefore, we will steer the nulls in azimuth only.

Figure 2 - Two-element null-steering array with $\lambda/4$ spacing and 90-degree phase shift.

Figure 3. Six-element circular phased-array antenna, with circular patch elements.

The array factor for this equally-excited six element array is [3]

$$\alpha_n = -(\pi/2)\cos[\phi_o - 2\pi(n/6)]$$

$$f(\theta) = \sum_{n=1}^6 e^{j\{(\pi/2)\sin\theta\cos[\phi - 2\pi(n/6)] + \alpha_n\}} \quad (2)$$

where

is the required phase shift for each n th element, when the main beam is steered toward the horizon, i.e., $\theta_o = 90$ degrees, and toward the azimuth angle, ϕ_o . The null will be directed opposite the main beam, or $\phi_o \pm \pi$ as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - Normalized array factor for six-element circular array, showing the steered null for six sets of progressive phase shifts.

Figure 5 - Ring array with half-wavelength diameter in free space, made from circular-patch elements that are half-wavelength with dielectric constant, $\epsilon_r = 5$.

To further suppress interfering power from horizontal angles, we used patch antennas as the elements, due to their antenna patterns as well as their polarization versatility. However, patch antennas typically resonate at frequencies that make the patches one-half wavelength in length [4]. In free space, the six half-wavelength patches would overlap each other. Fortunately, there is some forgiveness due to the dielectric constant of the material between the patch element and the ground plane. For example, if the dielectric constant were $\epsilon_r = 4$, the patch dimension would scale down by 50%. So a half-wavelength patch would actually only occupy a quarter wavelength of distance in free space, and fortunately, the array dimensions are determined in free space. Figure 5 shows a ring of half-wavelength patches, with $\epsilon_r = 5$, distributed along a ring with a diameter equaling one-half wavelength in free space. Clearly, these physically smaller half-wavelength patches fit without overlapping. In this case, S21 measurements between adjacent elements were -20dB, and even less the more separated elements. However, it is usually desirable to decrease the patch element size as much as possible.

One option to reduce the element size would be to use a dielectric that is high enough to achieve the desired reduction. However, higher dielectric constants reduce bandwidth, potentially to unacceptable levels. In order to further reduce the patch size without drastically decreasing bandwidth, circular patches were chosen as antenna elements to reduce corner dimensions. In addition, fractal-antenna techniques were incorporated, as shown in Figure 6, in order to reduce their physical size [5][6] and to maintain adequate bandwidth. The more size reduction that can be achieved using fractal designs, the lower that the dielectric constant of the substrate needs to be for a given size.

Figure 6 - Circular fractal patch element.

RESULTS

As previously discussed, patch antennas were chosen as the elements for this antenna array. Figure 7 is a measured antenna pattern in the elevation (vertical) plane, showing 10dB of attenuation at the horizon (90 and 270 degrees) compared to the zenith (0 degrees in the figure). The VSWR at resonance was 1.53, when fed 70% of the radius from the center of the circular patch. The six-element array was tested in an anechoic chamber for a specific azimuth null direction, and the resulting radiation pattern is shown in Figure 8. The measured azimuth pattern in Figure 8 agrees well with the simulated patterns of Figure 4. The measured pattern indicates that a 30-degree null can be created with 13dB of attenuation, which can be steered to the interference source. In order to get an idea of mutual coupling between elements, S21 measurements were taken between all elements in the array. Table 1 lists a sample set of S21 measurements between one of the elements the other five elements. These S21 measurements indicate that the isolation between elements is at least 20dB.

Table 1 – S-parameter measurements (in dB), indicating level of mutual coupling.

S – Parameter	Open	50 Ω
Base S_{11} *	-7.6	-
S_{11}	-6.9	-7.6
S_{21}	-19.0	-19.5
S_{31}	-28.8	-29.2
S_{41}	-32.5	-32.8
S_{51}	-29.2	-29.5
S_{61}	-19.5	-19.9

CONCLUSION

A six element array of circular patch antennas was constructed, resulting in radiation patterns than created 10dB nulls to the horizon in all 360-degrees of azimuth. The array created a steerable 30-degree null in the azimuth direction that attenuated an additional 13 dB. This radiation pattern of the null-steering array agreed well with the simulations. There was sufficient isolation between elements to avoid gross perturbation from mutual coupling between elements. This system was used to suppress a 20-Watt, 20-MHz jammer that was six feet from the satellite receiver to a SIR of better than 13dB. Since the system was adaptive, it was also able to suppress jamming signals that were moving relative to the satellite receiver.

Figure 7 - Measured elevation pattern of a single patch antenna element while in the circular array.

Figure 8 – Measured phased-array pattern in the azimuth plane.

References

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